

SOME MEASURES TO DEVELOP PROBLEM SOLVING CAPACITY IN TEACHING THE MODULE ON MARXIST- LENINIST PHILOSOPHY FOR STUDENTS AT SCHOOL OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES - THAI NGUYEN UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: Marxist-Leninist philosophy is a mandatory subject in the higher education curriculum in Vietnam. Philosophy aims to build the most basic knowledge bases of human thinking, which are worldview and methodology. Therefore, learning and teaching this subject must have close coordination between professional knowledge and teaching methods. In this article, the author offers a number of measures to develop problem-solving capacity in teaching the Marxist-Leninist philosophy module for students at School of Foreign Languages - Thai Nguyen University from actually teaching the subject.

Keywords: Competence, problem solving, students, Marxist-Leninist philosophy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to solve problems is an important ability for each person to adapt to the development of society. Forming and developing problem-solving capacity in the teaching process is an inevitable trend in education.

Marxist-Leninist philosophy is a subject that provides students with concepts and methods of perceiving the world. Compared to other subjects, the subjects of Marxist-Leninist philosophy are identified as the most common laws of existence, movement, and development of nature, society, and thinking. These laws are reflected through the system of principles, laws, and categories of Marxist-Leninist philosophy. During the process of studying this subject, the core and specific competency that students need to achieve is the ability to solve problems, in which students not only have the ability to perceive theoretical issues but also have to have the ability to apply this knowledge to solve practical problems with a positive spirit and attitude. The current practice of teaching this subject at the School of Foreign Languages - Thai Nguyen University shows that developing problem-solving capacity for students has not really been paid attention to, and innovation in teaching methods has not really been focused. Students are not really interested in learning because of the academic nature of the subject, and have not had experience in handling problematic situations during the learning process, thereby limiting their ability to adapt to life's problems as well as the practical demands of the profession. Thereby, the problem arises of finding measures to promote the development of students' problem-solving capacity during the process of studying the Marxist-Leninist Philosophy module.

II. CONTENT

1. Some related concepts

1.1. Capacity concept

“Competence is the ability to responsibly and effectively perform actions, solve tasks and problems in changing situations in professional, social or personal fields on the basis of understanding, skills, techniques and experience as well as being ready to act” [2, p 68].

According to the draft General Education Program: “Competence is the ability to successfully perform activities in a certain context thanks to the combined mobilization of knowledge, skills and other personal attributes such as interest, belief, will, etc. An individual's capacity is evaluated through the method and results of that individual's activities when solving life's problems" [1, p15].

Capacity in the most general sense is the ability that an individual demonstrates when participating in a certain activity at a certain time:

Competency is the ability to effectively perform a specific task/action, related to a certain field based on knowledge, skills, techniques and readiness to act. [3, p 7].

1.2. Teaching aims to develop problem-solving capacity

Problem-solving capacity:

Problem solving ability is the ability of people to operate intellectually in the face of specific, goal-oriented and highly targeted problems and problems that require mobilizing positive and creative thinking abilities to find a solution to the problem.

Problem solving ability can be understood as a person's ability to discover a problem that needs to be solved and know how to apply their own knowledge, skills, and experience, and be ready to take action to solve the problem well. Problem-solving ability is a combination of abilities expressed in skills (thinking operations and activities) in activities to effectively solve the tasks of the problem.

Teaching aims to develop problem-solving capacity

Problem-solving teaching is a teaching method based on the rules of knowledge acquisition and creative ways of working, with the basic features of scientific inquiry. This method creates "problem situations" and controls learners to solve those learning problems. Thanks to this, it ensures that learners firmly grasp scientific foundations, develop creative thinking capacity and form the basis of a scientific worldview. This method is often applied to complex learning content or tasks, requiring learners to analyze, explain, prove, and perform tasks.

Teaching problem solving is carried out flexibly in 4 main steps and in each step there are specific activities including:

Step 1: Recognize the problem

- Give a situation
- Create problem situations.
- In this step, it is necessary to analyze the given situation, explain and clarify it to properly understand the situation and identify the problem.
- State the problem: The problem should be clearly stated and the goal of solving that problem should be set.

Step 2: Research and plan to find solutions

- Analyze the problem, clarify the relationships between what is known and what must be found.
- Develop hypotheses about the problem in different directions.
- Make a plan to solve the problem
- Propose solutions, adjusting, even rejecting and redirecting when necessary.

Step 3: Implement the problem-solving plan

- Implement the problem solving plan. Test hypotheses using different methods. Check the correctness and practical relevance of the solution.

Step 4: Conclusion

- Discuss the results obtained and evaluate.

- Propose new related problems through analogy, generalization, overturning the problem and solving it if possible.

- Conclusion and application to new situations.

This process depends on many factors and the complexity of the research problem, the level of knowledge and cognitive ability of students. Therefore, the application process can be simpler or more complex.

In teaching, the process of teaching and solving problems does not necessarily have to follow a sequence of steps but can be flexibly applied accordingly.

2. Current status of developing problem-solving capacity for students during the process of teaching the Marxist-Leninist philosophy module at School of Foreign Languages - Thai Nguyen University

Clearly recognize the position, role and importance of problem-solving capacity in the learning and training process of students, especially the factors that directly impact improving students' problem-solving in the current period. The teaching staff and students of the School of Foreign Languages - Thai Nguyen University have made innovations in content, form, and measures to improve the quality of subject learning, such as: Organizing forums, exchanging experiences and methods of learning political theory subjects, especially subjects belonging to the laws and categories of philosophy, lecturers have been proactively creative in the teaching process such as history, using situations in the teaching and group discussion process, closely combined with the use of presentation technology to simulate and reproduce the content of lecture knowledge, at the same time, set requirements and tasks for students to solve to increase student interest in the subject.

Regarding teaching content: School of Foreign Languages - Thai Nguyen University teaches Marxist-Leninist philosophy for non-specialists, designed according to theoretical scientific content, focusing on the system of theoretical knowledge, the logical sequential development of principles, categories, concepts, perspectives. Lecturers teaching Marxist-Leninist philosophy must comply with the content and program of the Ministry of Education and Training. The difficulty is that the curriculum is purely theoretical, heavy on academic knowledge, so studying does not create excitement for students, or students do not have enough awareness and experience to receive knowledge. Therefore, during the teaching process, lecturers must focus on major problems, theoretical knowledge, and fundamental concepts to design teaching content into diverse and rich situations, stimulating students' interest in expressing their own views during the learning process.

On the lecturer's side: To meet the increasing requirements in teaching, in recent times, the school's lecturers have applied many modern teaching methods such as Problem-Based Learning (PBL) method, cooperative teaching method, flipped classroom, etc. and active teaching techniques such as brainstorming, picture galleries, tablecloths, thinking - sharing in pairs - sharing in front of the class, conversation combined with group discussion and reporting, investigation, research, games, role-playing, rhetoric skills, presentations, etc., commonly applied to develop students' capacity. Lecturers proficiently use modern teaching equipment such as projectors, computers, research rooms, libraries and teaching techniques, such as multimedia technology, specialized software for presentations, and graphic techniques. However, the integration of active teaching methods into the teaching process is at a low level. Especially the problem-solving teaching method, the number of lecturers who regularly use this method accounts for only 21.4%. Lecturers when teaching political theory subjects in general and Marxist-Leninist philosophy in particular determined that mainly use traditional teaching methods such as presentations, conversations... Some lecturers do not really understand the nature of problem-solving teaching and also do not have lectures using problem-solving methods for students.

Although lecturers apply active teaching methods and use modern technical means in the teaching process, those methods only emphasize how the learners work, not what the learners do. Lecturers have not built a foundation, sustainable learning methods, or even lifelong learning for students. Lecturers also have not really promoted the initiative and positivity of students in classroom construction, causing lecturers to create problem situations, determine goals, lesson

content, and solutions. It's quite common for students to have the skills to build their own awareness and always wait for the lecturer. Students being passive and relying on lecturers is also shown in the fact that when taking the final exam in the form of open questions, the ability to perceive, analyze and explain political and social issues is not good, leading to the situation of students not meeting the output standards or achieving them at an average or even weak level. Therefore, lecturers teaching the subject need to be clearly aware of developing problem-solving capacity for students to improve the quality of teaching the subject.

On the student side: Students' attitudes toward Marxist-Leninist philosophy also reveal some limitations such as: Their interest in learning about the subject is not much. Students feel that Marxist-Leninist philosophy is a "dry, difficult, and painful" subject, so they are reluctant to learn, and the teaching and learning methods are not suitable, passive learning, learning to cope to try to pass the subject, manifested in the process of studying this subject only memorizing the content in the textbook and lectures to review and take exams. Some students were initially interested in this subject, but due to unscientific methods of teaching and learning Marxist-Leninist philosophy, leading to low efficiency, their interest in the subject gradually lost.

3. Some measures to develop problem-solving capacity for students in the process of teaching the Marxist-Leninist philosophy module at School of Foreign Languages - Thai Nguyen University

3.1. Select appropriate content and use problem-solving teaching methods

Based on the requirements to be achieved in terms of knowledge content, using teaching methods to solve problems requires:

- There is a connection to the knowledge students already know.
- There are problematic situations or many understandings, different explanations or are associated with practical knowledge, many experiences and understanding.
- There must be certain difficulties that one person cannot solve alone, requiring group resolution.
- Pay attention to the amount of knowledge and implementation time.

When teaching about the relationship between matter and consciousness, the lecturer clarifies that this is a dialectical relationship. In which matter comes first, consciousness comes later, consciousness and matter are the source of consciousness that determines consciousness, consciousness affects matter through practical human activities. At the same time, if there is a problem situation, let the students debate and discuss the story of Poinsettia Mac Dinh Chi and a proverb of their ancestors "If there is a will, there is a way" to put students in a situation with material problems. Does it determine consciousness?

Or after finishing teaching the principles of common relationships and drawing out the methodological meaning, the lecturer can pose a problem for the students to solve within a certain period of time such as: "Currently, most students often live far away from their families and choose a fairly comfortable life of cohabitation before marriage." Do you agree with the above views and lifestyle? Why?

Or in the content of the role of practice in cognition, with 4 roles: basis (origin), motivation, purpose, and standards of cognition. The lecturer raised the problem: "Why did you choose the field you are studying? How do I know if I choose a major that suits my abilities?"

Just a few specific situations or examples for each specific content has helped students come to the subject more gently and easily understand the dry, abstract theory of the module.

3.2. Apply teaching in small groups to develop problem-solving capacity for students

Students are divided into separate small groups, responsible for a single goal, accomplished through each person's separate tasks. Separate individual activities are reorganized and organically linked together to achieve a common goal.

Small group teaching creates an environment in which students are willing to face challenges to dominate with knowledge and cooperate and empathize with others. This lays the foundation for the development of problem-solving capacity for students as individuals.

A group activity

Step 1. Work together as a whole class	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher introduces the discussion topic, raises the problem, and identifies the tasks. - Organize groups, assign tasks to groups, stipulate time and assign working positions to groups.
Step 2. Work in team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make a work plan. Agree on working rules - Assignment in groups, each individual works independently. - Exchange opinions and discuss in groups. - Appoint a representative to present the group's work results.
Step 3. Discuss and summarize in front of the whole class	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A representative of each group presents the results of the group's discussion. - Other groups observe, listen, question, comment and supplement. - The teacher summarizes and comments, raising questions for the next problem.

III. CONCLUSION

There are many different measures to develop problem-solving capacity for students during the process of teaching Marxist-Leninist philosophy at School of Foreign Languages - Thai Nguyen University. During this process, many problematic situations appear, especially situations related to the real life that students encounter every day. Therefore, lecturers need to give specific tasks for students to perform. Each task needs to have guiding questions for students to solve the problems and the tasks are solved through student activities to develop problem-solving capacity.

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